

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF TERRACE RICE CULTIVATION IN KOHIMA AND PHEK DISTRICTS OF NAGALAND

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ABSTRACT

Rice being principal cereal crop and having significant importance in northeast region the terrace rice cultivation has been shown to be a better farming system in rice cultivation compared to jhumming. The present study has been conducted in the Kohima and Phek districts of Nagaland to do a comparative study of the management practices and constraints faced by the 160 respondents by opting a purposively stratified randomly sampling technique. The respondents of both districts had similar package of practices in management differed between the selected districts with varying use of machineries, spacings and pest management methods. The average area and production of terrace rice per household were higher in Kohima district as compared to Phek district. T-test revealed a significant difference in the productivity of rice where Kohima had higher productivity. Regression analysis revealed area and pest management as the independent variables having significant effect on the production in both the districts. Less remunerative, less inputs and others consisting of pests and climatic factors were the most common problems faced by the terrace rice farmers in both districts while financial support, linking with government schemes / banks, others consisting of agri link roads construction and agriculture and allied departments intervention were the most relevant measures to promote terrace rice cultivation in both the districts.

Keywords: *Terrace Rice Cultivation, Management, Productivity, Constraints*

INTRODUCTION

Terraces, in agricultural context, are pieces of sloped planes cut into a series of successively receding flat surfaces or platforms used for the purposes of more effective farming (Singh *et al.* 2018). This type of landscaping is called terracing and the cultivation done thereof is called the terrace cultivation (Bhalerao *et al.* 2015). Terracing is also described as the interception and manipulation of slope along given direction (Ngachan, Mohanty and Pattanayak 2012). Terrace farming was said to have been invented by the *Inca* people who lived in the South American mountains (Vengota, 2011). Terrace cultivation has been practiced in China, Japan, Philippines, areas of Oceania and Southeast Asia; around the Mediterranean, in parts of Africa and in the Andes of South America for centuries. The Ifugao Rice Terraces in the Philippines is recognized as a world heritage site. Yunnan Honghe Hani Rice Terraces was designated as a Globally Important Agricultural Heritage Systems (GIAHS) in 2010. A research project run by the United Nations University and supported by the Asia Pacific Network for Global Change Research (APN) (2011-2013) on the rice terrace farming systems in Hani (China) and Ifugao (the Philippines) with an aim for providing ecosystem-based adaptation measures to strengthen the resilience of rice terrace farming systems to climate change, reduce the risk of flood and drought, and enhance existing systems to cope with climate change recognized socio-economic changes and their relevance to the sustainability of the terraces and expanded the project's scope to include issues of development and water management, in order to identify ways to strengthen current development strategies (Bhalerao *et al.* 2015). Ifugao terraces have shaped a characteristically landscape in the mountains between 800 and 1,500 meters. It is however, the availability of water that dictates the Ifugaos to build terraces. There are different types of terraces practised worldwide, the prominent ones being Broad and narrow

based terraces, Absorptive and Diversion-Type Terraces, Channel Terraces, Bench Terraces, Graded Trenching, level, broad-based and narrow based terraces, ridge terrace, etc. In India, terrace cultivation is practiced in the states of Punjab, Haryana, Plains of Uttar Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand and the North-eastern states. A cost-benefit analysis of terrace cultivation in Papung-Ben Khola watershed of Sikkim Himalaya shows that terracing is economically profitable as a conservation measure in the study watershed (Mishra and Rai, 2011).

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is the most important food grain crop of Nagaland and is grown in varying climatic and soil conditions i. e; rainfed upland jhum, rainfed lowlands and wet terrace rice cultivation. Even though Jhum cultivation is predominantly followed by the tribal communities in the state for rice cultivation, terrace rice cultivation is practiced by the different tribes in the state depending upon the topography and terrain. However, wet terrace rice cultivation is predominant in the Kohima and Phek districts of Nagaland (Anon. 2022a). The terraces meant for cultivation, particularly rice, have been made manually and the skills thereof, has been handed down through the generations. It is a labour-intensive process. The factors like soil erosion and run-off are controlled by terracing, and it helps in the retention of water, which is very important for cultivation of rice. The farmers have been passed on the techniques and skills through the generations whilst remaining unchanged except for use of machineries.

Terrace fields in these two districts are being used for cultivation of crops like rice, potato, garlic and cabbage where rice and potato are the two main crops grown in the Southern Angami areas of Kohima district. Nagaland being a hilly region, graduated terrace steps are commonly used for cultivation purpose. The Chakhesangs also practice a special type of farming called Zabo system, which is a farming system with the combination of forest and agriculture, terraces, fishery, and based on soil and water conservation principles (Anon. 2021).

The area and production of rice in Jhum and Wet Terrace Rice Cultivation is observed that the area, production, and productivity of rice under WTRC are higher than that of Jhum cultivation in both the districts. There was also an increase in the area, production, and productivity of WTRC in both the districts in 2017-2018 as compared to 2016-2017 (Anon. 2018). With the increase in population and the impending problems of food security, there is a need to search for improved cultivation practices in order to meet the increasing demands. As such, Wet Terrace Rice Cultivation proves to be a better alternative to jhum cultivation in many fronts, although the labour and capital involved is high initially. The rural society in Nagaland is still deeply rooted in the traditional practices of agriculture. However, with the recent exposure of the farmers to improved technologies and techniques in agriculture, the sector has seen a paradigm shift in the practices. Nevertheless, the gender roles and also the management practices in the agricultural society largely remain the same, so the present research was undertaken to make a comparative study.

Although Terraced Rice Cultivation is predominant in the two districts, very little research has been done in the field concerned. There is a lack of academic research in the economics of terrace cultivation in the two districts. So, there is a need to further study in detail about the making a comparison amongst them. There is also a need to identify the problems and constraints that is hampering the farmers in adoption, management, or practices in terrace cultivation to

answer the questions viz; Is there any significant difference in the production and productivity of terrace rice between the two districts? Are there any differences in the practices and management of terrace rice cultivation among the farmers in the two districts? What are the problems and constraints faced by the terrace rice farmers? Are the constraints same for the farmers of the two districts?

To study the similarities and differences in the management factors, and the production and productivity in terrace rice cultivation between the two districts, and to study the constraints faced by farmers in the two districts.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Primary data were collected personally from the selected respondents through structured schedules and questionnaires especially designed for this study. Secondary data were collected from various publications, journals, articles, handbooks, annual reports, annual employment reviews by Government of Nagaland, Directorate of Agriculture, etc. The study was conducted in the Kohima and Phek districts of Nagaland state due to the relevance of the study in the two districts. Kohima district is the home of the Angami and Rengma Naga tribes. As of 2021, it is the second most populous district of Nagaland with a population of 2,87,688. Kohima district is subdivided into the eight administrative circles of Tseminyu, Tsogin, Chiephobozou, Botsa, Kezocha, Jakhama, Kohima Sadar and Sechu-Zubza. Terrace Rice Cultivation is most predominant in the district. Phek is a hilly district of Nagaland. It is home to the Chakhesang and Pochury Naga tribes. It has a population of 163,418. Agriculture is the main occupation with 80.84 per cent of the population engaged in agriculture. The district is split into 14 administrative circles, which are Pfutsero, Phek Sadar, Chetheba, Chozuba, Meluri, Sekruzu, Chizami, Sakraba, Razieba, Zuketsa, Phor, Khuza, Khezhakeno, and Phokhungri. Terrace Rice cultivation is the most predominant practice in the district.

Nagaland state was selected purposively for conducting the study due to the familiarity and convenience of the researcher so districts were selected purposively for the proposed study because of their popularity and relevance in terrace rice cultivation, in the second stage 4 blocks / administrative circles were purposively selected from each district; based on the number of villages practising TRC for a proper representation of the sample population. For Kohima district, Jakhama, Sechu Zubza, Chiephobozou and Botsa were selected as TRC is most prevalent in these blocks. Similarly, for Phek district, Pfutsero, Chetheba, Zuketsa and Meluri were selected for the study. The total number of was 8. Two villages from each block were selected purposively based on the relevance and importance of TRC practice. From the 16 selected villages; a total of 160 respondents were selected randomly however the survey was carried from February 2022 to January 2024. The collected data were processed and analysed in accordance with the objectives of the study using SPSS 24 version software. T-statistics was used for comparing the rice productivity means between Kohima and Phek. A linear regression model equation was fitted where production was taken as the dependant variable and other factors like management, land holdings, etc; as independent variables.

The multiple regression models (Gujarati, 2003) may be specified as,

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \beta_7X_7 + \beta_8X_8 + \beta_9X_9 + e_i,$$

Whereas: Y = Production output (kg); x_1 = Area (Scale); x_2 = Nursery bed preparation method; x_3 = Spacing (Scale); x_4 = Weeding (Scale); x_5 = Manure application (Scale); x_6 = Ploughing and machinery use; x_7 = Pest management (Scale); x_8 = Disease management (Scale); x_9 = Time spent in farm activities; α = Constant; and e_i =

error term. However, for the study of constraints, 5- points Likert scale was used for recording the responses and analysis was done using descriptive statistics tools like mean, mean sum of squares and standard deviation following the methods of Likert (1932). The responses for agreement were 1-Strongly disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree and 5-Strongly agree. The mean of the responses for each statement was 3. The mean of the responses for each statement was taken and the standard deviation was drawn. Statements with mean less than 3 was classified as disagree, equal to 3 as neutral and greater than 3 as agree. Based on the responses selected by the respondents, simple percentages were used for drawing suitable suggestions to promote terrace rice cultivation in the two districts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 reveals that a multiple regression model was fitted to explain the production based on the different management factors. The Durbin-Watson test value of 1.735, which is above 1.50, indicated that there is no first-order autocorrelation between the independent variables however there is positive correlation between the variables. A co-efficient of multiple determination (R^2) value of 0.764 indicates that 76.40 per cent of the variance in the production is explained by the independent variables which show a good fit of the selected model. The result is consistence with the work of Alam and Effendy (2017); Tangjang and Sharma (2021).

Table 1. Model Summary (j) of regression co-efficient of Kohima

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
J	.874(i)	.764	.734	468.78992	1.735

i Predictors: (Constant), area_kohima, nursery_bed_preparation_kohima, spacing_kohima, weeding_kohima, manure_kohima, ploughingandmachinery_kohima, pestmanagement_kohima, diseasemanagement_kohima, Time_spent_in_farm_kohima and j Dependent Variable: production_kohima

Table 2. Regression coefficients of variables of Kohima

Model J	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	R^2
	Beta	B	Standard Error	
(Constant)	-	-.749	.456	0.764
Area	.853*	13.829*	.000*	
Nursery bed preparation	.029	.490	.626	
Spacing	.026	.411	.683	
Weeding	.056	.935	.353	
Manure	.059	.947	.347	
Ploughing and machinery use	.085	1.223	.226	
Pest management	.157*	2.581*	.012*	
Disease management	-.024	-.358	.722	
Time spent in farm	-.017	-.253	.801	

*j Dependent Variable: production_kohima, *5 per cent level of significance*

Table 2 reveals that among the independent variables affecting production, area ($t = 13.829$) and pest management ($t = 2.581$) had significant effect on the production at 5 per cent level of significance. This implies that for every unit increase in area, production increases by 0.853. Likewise for every unit increase in pest management, production increases by 0.157. The independent variables like nursery bed preparation method, spacing, weeding,

manure application, ploughing and machinery use, disease management, time spent in farm activities had no significant relation to the production. These results are consistent with some other studies on Nagaland by Das *et al.* (2012); Borah and Sharma (2015); Chidi, Anozhi and Chinaja (2015); Venyo and Sharma (2018); Longkumer and Giribabu (2019); Yadav, Sharma and Singh (2021).

Table 3 reveals that a multiple regression model was fitted to explain the production based on the different management factors. The Durbin-Watson test value of 1.823, which is above 1.5, indicated that there is no first-order autocorrelation between the independent variables however there is positive correlation between the variables. A coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) value of 0.670 indicates that 67.00 per cent of the variance in the production is explained by the independent variables which show a good fit of the selected model. The result is consistency with the work of Tun and Hye-Jung (2015); Hoang *et al.* (2019); Mozhui and Sharma (2020).

Table 3. Model Summary (j) of regression co-efficient of Phek

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
j	.819(i)	.670	.628	389.71002	1.823

i Predictors: (Constant), area_phek, nursery_bed_preparation_phek, spacing_phek, weeding_phek, manure_application_phek, ploughingandmachinery_phek, pestmanagement_phek, diseasemanagement_phek, time_spent_in_farm_phek and *j* Dependent Variable: production_phek

Table 4 reveals that among the independent variables affecting production, area ($t=10.384$) and pest management ($t = -2.685$) had significant effect on the production at 5 per cent level of significance. This implies that for every unit increase in area, production increases by 0.743. The pest management showed significant negative effect on the production ($t = -.234$). The negative sign implies that poor pest management techniques resulted in poor production outcome. The independent variables like nursery bed preparation method, spacing, weeding, manure application, ploughing and machinery use, disease management, time spent in farm activities had no significant relationship to the production. Waris *et al.* (2016); Yumnam, Kumar and Chauhan (2016) confirmed that area is a key factor to increase the income as it helps the households to earn from different sources.

Table 4. Regression coefficients of variables of Phek

Model j	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	R ²
	Beta	B	Standard Error	
(Constant)	-	.309	.758	0.670
Area	.743*	10.384*	.000	
Nursery bed preparation	-.065	-.877	.383	
Spacing	.064	.864	.391	
Weeding	-.011	-.135	.893	
Manure	.097	.957	.342	
Ploughing and machinery use	.114	1.532	.130	
Pest management	-.234*	-2.685*	.009	
Disease management	-.098	-1.279	.205	
Time spent in farm	.068	.701	.486	

j Dependent Variable: production_phek, *5 per cent level of significance

The regression analysis results show that among the different independent variables, area had significant effect on the dependent production variable in the two districts. While the pest management in Kohima was more varied in methods used and showed positive significance to the production, only rat trap was used for pest management in Phek.

Table 5. Reasons for not involving in non-farm activities in Kohima district

Constraints	SD	D	N	A	SA	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remarks
Lack of Time	9	20	20	27	4	2.96	1.11	Disagree
Lack of Knowledge	12	25	28	11	4	2.76	1.08	Disagree
Lack of finance	11	22	20	25	2	3.97	0.89	Agree
Inaccessibility of roads	7	44	24	5	0	2.33	0.72	Disagree
Marketing Problem	10	41	22	4	3	2.36	0.90	Disagree
Lack of raw materials	11	41	19	8	1	2.77	0.79	Disagree
Lack of demands	12	40	22	3	3	3.11	0.95	Agree
Lack of space	11	40	17	11	1	2.83	1.03	Disagree
Others	0	0	57	19	4	3.33	0.57	Agree

(1-Strongly disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree and 5-Strongly agree)

Table 5 reveals the reasons for not involving in non-farm activities by the respondents in Kohima district. Out of the given reasons, lack of finance, lack of demand and others were agreed as the reasons for not involving in non-farm activities in terrace rice cultivation by the respondents while the reasons like lack of time, like of knowledge, inaccessibility of roads, marketing problems, lack of raw materials and lack of space were disagreed to be the reasons for not involving in non-farm activities by the respondents. The same type of result was found by Medhi *et al.* (2020) in their study.

Table 6 reveals the reasons for not involving in non-farm activities by the respondents in Phek district. Out of the given reasons, lack of time, lack of knowledge, lack of finance and others were agreed to be the reasons for not involving in non-farm activities in terrace rice cultivation by the respondents while the reasons like inaccessibility of roads, marketing problems, lack of raw materials, lack of demands and lack of space were disagreed to be the reasons for not involving in non-farm activities by the respondents. The result is consistence with the work of Kithan (2014); Jayahari and Sen (2015); Singh and Devi (2018).

Table 6. Reasons for not involving in non-farm activities in Phek district

Constraints	SD	D	N	A	SA	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remarks
Lack of Time	0	25	8	38	9	3.38	1.04	Agree
Lack of Knowledge	0	41	10	22	7	3.38	0.99	Agree
Lack of finance	0	39	16	22	3	3.50	0.96	Agree
Inaccessibility of roads	1	44	15	16	4	2.72	0.96	Disagree
Marketing Problem	1	73	5	1	0	2.07	0.34	Disagree
Lack of raw material	1	78	1	0	0	2.00	0.15	Disagree
Lack of demands	1	78	1	0	0	2.00	0.15	Disagree
Lack of space	1	76	1	0	2	2.07	0.49	Disagree
Others	0	0	57	19	4	3.33	0.57	Agree

(1-Strongly disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree and 5-Strongly agree)

Table 7 reveals the problems faced by the respondents in terrace rice cultivation in Kohima district. Out of the given reasons, less remunerative, lack of storage space, lack of inputs and others (pests, climatic factors) were agreed to be the main constraints faced by the respondents in Kohima district. The constraints like lack of planting materials / seeds, not regular work and farming is difficult were disagreed to be the constraints faced by respondents

in the district. This result is supported by some other similar types of study e.g. Sashimatsang (2015); Pamela and Sharma (2021); Yani and Sharma (2022).

Table 7. Problems in TRC in Kohima district

Constraints	SD	D	N	A	SA	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remarks
Lack of Planting materials	20	45	10	5	0	2.00	0.79	Disagree
Less remunerative	0	5	34	31	10	3.57	0.79	Agree
Not Regular work	6	47	16	10	1	2.41	0.85	Disagree
Lack of proper storage	1	3	13	31	32	4.12	0.90	Agree
Lack of inputs	1	8	24	28	19	3.70	0.98	Agree
Farming is difficult	2	28	21	27	2	2.98	0.94	Disagree
Others (pests, climatic factor)	1	1	20	36	22	3.96	0.83	Agree

(1-Strongly disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree and 5-Strongly agree)

Table 8 reveals the problems faced by the respondents in terrace rice cultivation in Phek district. Out of the given reasons, less remunerative, lack of inputs and others (pests, climatic factors) were agreed to be the main constraints faced by the respondents in Phek district. The constraints like lack of planting materials/seeds, not regular work, lack of storage space, and farming is difficult were disagreed to be the constraints faced by respondents in the district. This result contradicts with the findings of Nath and Das (2017); Singh *et al.* (2018).

Table 8 Problems in TRC in Phek district

Constraints	SD	D	N	A	SA	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remarks
Lack of Planting materials	41	34	4	1	0	1.56	0.65	Disagree
Less remunerative	0	11	25	31	13	3.57	0.92	Agree
Not Regular work	2	49	26	3	0	2.37	0.60	Disagree
Lack of proper storage	2	73	3	2	0	2.06	0.40	Disagree
Lack of inputs	0	2	23	28	27	4.00	0.85	Agree
Farming is difficult	2	40	24	14	0	2.62	0.80	Disagree
Others (pests, climatic factors)	1	3	18	30	28	4.01	0.92	Agree

(1-Strongly disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree and 5-Strongly agree)

Table 9. Measures to promote TRC in Kohima district

Measures	Frequency	Total
Financial Support	50 (62.50)	80 (100.00)
Constitution of SHG/FO	11 (13.75)	80 (100.00)
More awareness programme	38 (47.50)	80 (100.00)
More training	35 (43.75)	80 (100.00)
Linking with Govt. Scheme/Bank	52 (65.00)	80 (100.00)
Others(agri link roads, agri and allied depts. intervention)	45 (56.25)	80 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates the percentage to the total)

Table 9 reveals the measures to promote terrace rice cultivation in Kohima district. 65.00 per cent of the respondents ranked Linking with Govt. Schemes / banks as the main measure to promote TRC in Kohima district followed by the measures like financial support (62.50 per cent), others consisting of agri link roads and agri and allied departments intervention (56.25 per cent), more awareness programme (47.50 per cent), more training (43.75

per cent) and constitution of SHG / FO (13.75 per cent). Measures to promote the TRC households having better skilled of members will be contributing to enhance the family income by Ly *et al.* (2016); Kumar and Singh (2019); Krishnakutty *et al.* (2021).

Table 10. Measures to promote TRC in Phek district

Measures	Frequency	Total
Financial Support	39 (48.75)	80 (100.00)
Constitution of SHG/FO	00 (00.00)	80 (100.00)
More awareness programme	15 (18.75)	80 (100.00)
More training	08 (10.00)	80 (100.00)
Linking with Govt. Scheme/Bank	20 (25.00)	80 (100.00)
Others(agri link roads, agri and allied depts. intervention)	33 (41.25)	80 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates the percentage to the total)

Table 10 reveals the measures to promote terrace rice cultivation in Phek district. 48.75 per cent of the respondents ranked financial support as the main measure to promote TRC in Phek district followed by the measures like others consisting of agri link roads and agri and allied departments intervention (41.25 per cent), linking with Government scheme / banks (25.00 per cent), more awareness programme (18.75 per cent) and more training (10.00 per cent). Measures to promote the TRC households having better skilled of members will be contributing to enhance the family income by Dewan *et al.* (2019); Kulyakware *et al.* (2020); Borah and Sharma (2021).

CONCLUSION

The outcomes of the study indicate that terrace rice cultivation has shown to be a better farming practice compared to jhum cultivation in terms of enhancing production through management factors. For a hilly and mountainous region, terrace cultivation benefits the environment through soil and water conservation. Though the increase in area will definitely lead to an increase in the production, the limited land area and the cost of expanding area under terrace will be a constraint and prove to be less remunerative for the farmers who are in need of financial support to do the same. Therefore, the rejuvenation of the existing terrace rice fields in both the districts by proper nutrient management, pest management, disease management and soil testing will help in enhancing the rice productivity per unit area. The role of government schemes and financial institutions in incentivizing cultivation will greatly bolster the rice production under terrace rice cultivation. The construction of proper agri link roads will also greatly ease the convenience of cultivation by means of mechanization and easy accessibility, thereby, promote the development of new terraces and rejuvenation of abandoned terraces. The intervention of the agriculture and allied departments in timely identification of the common problems faced owing to pests, diseases, and losses due to climatic factors like flooding, hailstorms, landslides, etc., will aid in mitigation and prevention of production losses. There is a greater need to study the package of practices in terrace rice cultivation in order to pave way for sustainable production system in the future whilst incentivizing the farmers.

Declarations

i). It's to declared that all the authors have agreed to the submission of this research work in this Journal. Names (in order) and affiliations have been appropriately added to the paper. The paper has not been submitted elsewhere. All the used content has been properly cited. The research is an independent work and No agency / organization has sponsored the same. Data, results and inferences are correct and not influenced by any party / person / agency.

ii). It is declared that only the authors have the authority of using the domain knowledge discussed in the paper for any kind of financial benefit. All used references have been duly acknowledged, wherever applicable.

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